

THE ESSENCE AND SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES.

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Annotation: This article focuses on the scientific nature of educational technology, its essence, specifics and its application in solving specific problems.

Keywords: educational technology, integration, elements of educational technology, concept of technology

The role of educational technologies in improving the education system, revising the content of personnel training based on the priority tasks of the country's social and economic development, and preparing educated specialists at the level of international standards is incomparable.

Today, the formation of new social relations in our society, the integration of education into the world education system, the development of democratization and humanization processes require a new approach to modern educational technologies in the educational process.[1]

Technology is derived from the Greek word "techne" which means skill, art, and the word "logos" means information. "Technology" means the sum of knowledge about the methods and means of implementing processes, as well as the quality changes that occur in the object. Educational technology is taught to students in certain conditions with the help of teaching tools of the teacher (pedagogue). as a result of the systemic impact it has, it can be described as a social phenomenon that intensively shapes the necessary and predetermined social qualities in them.[2]

Educational technology is a system for creating, applying and determining the process of all teaching and knowledge acquisition, taking into account human and technical resources and their interaction, in order to optimize forms of education.

The essence and principles of personalized learning technologies:

- In the course of teaching, educational goals expressed based on the requirements of pedagogical technologies are achieved. In the period of accelerated scientific and technical development, the effectiveness of teaching mainly depends on the role of the student in the teaching process and the attitude of the pedagogue towards him.
- In authoritarian technology, the pedagogue appears as the only subject. Pupils only act as objects. In this case, the student's initiative and independence are lost, teaching is carried out in a compulsory manner. Typical traditional teaching refers to authoritarian technology. First of all, Y.A. It is meant to be organized in the "classroom" system of teaching based on the principles of didactics expressed by Comenius. The "classroom" system of teaching is still the most widespread in the world.

Advanced educational technologies - the educational process is more focused on the person of the learner, the non-traditional form of teaching, interactive methods and a set of modern educational tools are used in educational work. is to guide the achievement of the desired goal.

Collaborative learning technology - realizing that collaborative learning technology leads to the success of every learner in his studies, to regularly and diligently work mentally, to perform educational tasks with quality, to thoroughly master the educational material, to comrades becomes a partner and prepares the ground for the organization of mutual assistance.[3]

Computer-based educational technology is teaching based on the use of a computer, which is based on unlimited teaching, with the possibility of rapid management of the teaching process at an optimal level and creating psychological comfort.

In short, educational technologies implement all the cognitive processes shown in the training sessions, and ultimately help to fully master all types of activities. education carried out with, the stages of the classical system are preserved.

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